
CSCCE Tech Tip Sheet - Zoom bombing: How to deal with bad actors during Zoom events

Introduction

Safety is an important consideration if you are regularly convening virtual events. “Zoom bombing,” where a bad actor joins your meeting and disrupts the proceedings in some way, is not just a nuisance. It can be a distressing experience for your participants. In this tip sheet, we provide a checklist of things to do before, during, and after your event to help you and your team prepare for such an eventuality and to minimize any harm it might cause.

Anecdotally, Zoom bombing is more prevalent when hosting [Zoom meetings](#), and less of an issue for [Zoom webinars](#), likely because webinars may be configured to offer a more limited number of ways for attendees to participate (for example, no attendee videos are visible, chat may be turned off, and any questions for the speakers can be submitted directly to the host). If you have access to Zoom webinars, and that format is appropriate for your event, this is one way to increase security. This tip sheet focuses on what to do when your Zoom meeting is interrupted, although some of the same strategies for communicating with your team and event participants are applicable to both meetings and webinars.

In preparing this tip sheet, we conducted a “safety drill,” where we role-played an incident with members of our community. This is a useful exercise to try with your team. As well as highlighting the numerous ways Zoom bombers can interfere if given the opportunity (for example, via screen sharing, changing their profile information, and co-opting the chat and/or direct messages), it also allows you to familiarize yourself with how to respond - and what happens when you take different actions, such as temporarily suspending participant capabilities. During our safety drill, we discussed the importance of empowering team and community members to help address the meeting disruption, should one occur. The first step: if you see something, say something! Help out the meeting organizers by proactively telling them if someone is behaving badly during a call.

This problem is of course not unique to the Zoom platform. This tip sheet focuses on Zoom because we are aware of how many members of our community routinely use it for their meetings and events. Our intention here is to neither endorse nor critique Zoom. Instead, we hope that the checklist and practical tips below will support you in scenario planning so that you feel prepared to address any disruptions if you do have to deal with a bad actor.

Before the event

Putting in some preparation before your event will help you to more smoothly address any problems that arise in the moment. The key here is empowering both the organizing team and community

members - including having clear lines of communication set up in advance. Much of this preparatory work will be reusable for future meetings.

SECURITY OPTIONS ON ZOOM

Take a few moments to check your Zoom admin settings by logging in via the Zoom browser interface. You may need to balance between reducing barriers to entry and setting more restrictive permissions to make the meeting secure. For example, for a small meeting you may not require attendees to pre-register as you're not promoting the event widely. Note that Zoom regularly updates their processes and security options. One way to stay informed is to [subscribe to the Zoom blog](#) to receive regular emails about updates.

- Check that you're running the latest version of Zoom - and **install any updates**. To do so, open the Zoom application you are running and select "Check for Updates" from the "zoom.us" drop-down menu. You can also download and install new versions [through the Zoom website](#). This applies to all Zoom license types.
- Consider using the authentication feature**, which only allows registered Zoom users to join the meeting, or users from within a particular organization. You can also request all participants [register for your meeting](#) ahead of time.
- Enable the waiting room** feature so that attendees will need to be admitted to the main room by a host or co-host. Plan to carefully monitor participants relative to your attendee list.
- Consider setting screen sharing to "host only."** You can then allow individuals to screen share as needed.
- Turn off annotation for anyone other than the person who is presenting** (unless, of course, your planned activities require everyone to have access to this feature).
- Turn off the option for removed participants to rejoin.** This is critical, and will ensure that once you evict the Zoom bomber they cannot click on the meeting link again and come back in.
- You can also decide whether to allow participants to **change their screen names** and **display their profile pictures**, both of which can be manipulated in negative ways.
- Turn on "report to Zoom,"** which gives you the option in a meeting to report a trouble-maker.
- For large groups, you may wish to **turn on and off the group chat as needed**, e.g., to respond to activities at specific times during the meeting.

PREPARATION AND CONTINGENCY PLANS

Next, you need to plan your communications with attendees to help them create a safe meeting. You'll also be better supported if you have a team of colleagues or volunteers to help with event management.

Communicating with your participants

By communicating with participants ahead of the meeting, you can explain how you are working to keep the meeting safe and what to expect if a disruption occurs.

- Ask for participants to use the name they prefer to be addressed by, and not a default organizational account name or shortened username**, as their Zoom name so that you can identify them when they join the waiting room. If you have implemented a registration requirement, you could also ask that the name they use on Zoom matches the name they used for registration.
- Share the primary meeting link with participants via a secure medium**, e.g., by email. Ask clearly that participants do not share links on social media to protect the meeting space.
- Explain to the participants how they can report a disruption**, e.g., don't interact directly with the perpetrator, take screenshots or other details, if possible, and direct message a designated member of the organizing team who will assist in reporting and removing the offender. You may want to identify organizers in some way - such as via prefixes on their screen names.
- Explain what would happen should the meeting link be compromised**, e.g., how you would share a new link in the community Slack channel or event email list.
- Create a backup meeting link** that you can be ready to share with your participants. This might be a recurring meeting that you always have ready to go (but if you do have to use it, retire it afterwards and make a new backup).

Key roles / team set up

- Assign roles** to members of your code of conduct committee, colleagues, or others supporting the event so that it's clear who will do what if an incident occurs. Roles might include:
 - Documenting the incident, e.g., via screenshots
 - Reaching out to affected participants to provide support
 - Communications / technical controls during the incident (this person should be the host in Zoom. Co-hosts do not have the same level of control and cannot, for example, lock the meeting.)
 - Communications to restart the event
 - Reporting the incident to Zoom
- Provide training or a checklist** of actions to take (such as the ones below!) to help your teammates feel empowered to take action should anything happen.
- Identify a community leader or staff member who is particularly good under pressure**. Not everyone can think clearly when panicked, and that is totally normal.
- Have a plan for how you will communicate with your co-host(s)** in case you need to disable all participant features. While this setting is activated you will not be able to use Zoom to

communicate with them as their participation will have been suspended, too. You might use a dedicated Slack channel or text message thread instead.

- ❑ **If you have access to information technology (IT) support, find out who you should contact** in case of an incident. Your IT department may also be able to provide additional information specific to your institution or organization, as well as support when and if you need to submit a report to Zoom.

What to do in the moment

How you react to a disruption of your meeting will depend on the nature of it, and how easily you or your team can neutralize the bad actors. We offer two pathways to follow, depending on how many Zoom bombers you're dealing with. Your exact response may be a variation on these protocols, depending on your particular context.

ONE ZOOM BOMBER

- ❑ If you can easily spot the bad actor, use the menu to the right of their name to **immediately report them**.
- ❑ Then, use the same menu to **remove them from the meeting**. As long as you have configured your meeting accordingly (see above), the removed person will not be able to rejoin the call.
- ❑ Now, you can **communicate to your team** about the situation through your designated back channel (e.g., a team Slack channel or text thread). Ask yourselves:
 - Do we need a new link?
 - If you have the waiting room enabled, you may feel confident that you can monitor that for any other intruders. This might be the best course of action for small, relatively short meetings.
 - You might also consider locking the meeting, but be aware that this prevents *anyone* from joining, including well-intentioned participants who might be running late.
 - Should we resume?
 - Depending on the nature of the incident, you might want to cancel the meeting and reconvene at another time.
 - If you decide to resume, consider polling your participants directly in Zoom to make sure they feel comfortable proceeding.
- ❑ Whatever you decide, clearly **communicate your contingency plan to your attendees**.
- ❑ If you decided to move to a new link, **drop the new link into the chat**, and then close down the existing meeting.
- ❑ Once everyone rejoins the new link, take a moment to **explain what happened** and to **reiterate the process for asking for help**.

MULTIPLE ZOOM BOMBERS (OR ONE ZOOM BOMBER IN A BIG MEETING)

- Click the security button on the tool bar in Zoom and immediately click “**Suspend Participant Activities.**” This will immediately stop any screen sharing, mute everyone, and prevent participants from using the chat. It will also lock the meeting so that no one else can join.
- NOTE: this action also suspends all co-host capabilities,** so you as the host will be on your own, or relying on your back channel to communicate with your team.
- Record what happened in as much detail as you can** (e.g., snap a screenshot of the whole screen, download the chat, note down the user ID, etc.).
- Report any of the Zoom bombers** that you can identify, and then **remove them** from the meeting.
- At this point, you might be concerned about other bad actors that you have been unable to identify, so in this instance **do not drop the link to the new meeting into the chat.** Instead, go back into the security menu in the Zoom tool bar and toggle the settings to restart the meeting with restricted permissions (no webcams, mics, screen-sharing etc.). Then, let your participants know where to find a new link (e.g., in a forthcoming email or in your Slack channel).
- Once everyone rejoins the new link, take a moment to **explain what happened** and to **reiterate the process for asking for help.**

Follow up

After a Zoom bombing incident, it’s crucial that you take care of yourself and your participants. It can be a jarring experience, and could make you and your community members feel violated. Here are some suggestions to help you work through the aftermath.

- While you must ensure the privacy of your participants, which is particularly important if a Zoom bomber disrupts the meeting by targeting people via direct message, you should **let your participants know what is happening in general terms as soon as you can.** It can be disconcerting for a meeting to suddenly shut down with no ability to reconnect.
- If and when you restart the meeting, **acknowledge what happened and explain what you have done** to keep the meeting as secure as possible.
- If possible (e.g., if you have an email list of registrants or a Slack channel in which it would be appropriate to post), **send a personal message to all participants,** especially those directly affected, and offer an opportunity to talk about the incident. This may help refine your procedure going forward.
- Make it clear how anyone affected, including those that you may not know about, can **report further details about the incident and seek support.**
- Check in with your team.** Everyone handles things differently, and prior experiences might make dealing with a Zoom bomber more or less traumatic. Take some time to talk about what happened, leaving space for open-ended discussion before moving on to refining your protocols.

- Don't blame yourself!** This kind of incident can happen to anyone, and you as the organizer are not the one at fault.

HOW TO REPORT THE INCIDENT

Zoom has detailed [instructions for reporting violations](#) of its terms of use. If you are unable to report a user during the meeting, there is an option to report them after the meeting is over. You can also upload screenshots or other evidence of the incident. Reports are sent to the Zoom Trust and Safety team, who evaluate the incident and may choose to block the user. In the United States, [Zoom bombing is a federal offense](#) that may be prosecuted.

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